

Comparative analysis of optical data from Solzan landfill storage cards

Petrov K.V.¹, Khreptugova A.N.¹, Larionov K.S.¹, Vladimirov S.A.¹, Pechnikova G.S.¹, Zhurba V.S.¹, Perminova I.V.¹

¹Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Chemistry, Moscow, Russia
mnbv21228@mail.ru

Keywords: sludge lignin, Baikalsk pulp and paper mill, mass-spectrometry, fluorescence
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338166

Operational quality control of the aquatic environment in industrial waste storage areas is a critically important task. The above-sludge waters of the Baikalsk Pulp and Paper Mill storage cards, which pose a potential threat to the Baikalsk ecosystem in the event of a violation of the integrity of the enclosing dams, were chosen as the object of the study [1]. Optical methods are used in this study to quickly and efficiently analyze the composition of dissolved organic matter (DOM). Their effectiveness is based on the correlation between the absorption and fluorescent properties of DOM and its molecular characteristics. The aim of the work is to evaluate the spatial differentiation of the parameters of the DOM in above-sludge storage waters in order to identify statistically significant trends in their differences.

The dataset was created on the basis of 82 samples of above-sludge waters analyzed using fluorescence spectroscopy and UV-visible spectrometry. Absorption and excitation-emission matrix (EEM) spectra were used to calculate optical descriptors. Fluorescence emission band asymmetry, indicative of protein fluorescence contribution, was calculated as the ratio of integrated intensities at 350 nm excitation in the blue (420-460 nm) and red (550-600 nm) spectral regions. Humic and fluorescent indices were also calculated for fluorescence. Using data on the organic carbon content, the SUVA parameter characterizing the aromaticity of the DOM was calculated.

The purpose of the study is to establish patterns of spatial distribution of key characteristics (optical descriptors: Asm_{350} , $SUVA_{254}$, FI, HI) between different storage cards. To identify trends, the cluster analysis method is used to group storage cards according to similar characteristics. Statistical data processing was performed, including ANOVA analysis of variance to test the hypothesis of the significance of differences between the average values of indicators in different maps. Spatial trends were visualized and analyzed by constructing cartographic models (maps of isolines) of the distribution of descriptors. In order to confirm the results obtained by optical methods, the Fourier transform mass spectrometry (FT-ICR MS) method was applied.

It was found that in lignin storage cards (2 and 3) there is a strong correlation ($r = 0.9 - 1$) of spectral asymmetry Asm_{350} with the fluorescent index FI, and a very strong inverse correlation ($r = -0.85 - -0.94$) of Asm_{350} and FI with the humic index HI, whereas for ash storage cards such a correlation is not observed. The fourth storage card is unique in its correlation of the humic index with the asymmetry of the spectrum ($r = 0.8$), while for the remaining cards this value is less than zero ($r = -0.5 - -0.9$).

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation, grant No. 075-15-2024-533. The study was performed using the equipment of "Human Proteome" Core Facilities of the Institute of Biomedical Chemistry (Russia).

References

[1] Chebykin, E., Dambinov, Yu., Suturin, A. (2020). Multi-element analysis of above-sludge waters in the accumulation cells of Baikalsk pulp and paper mill for territory remediation strategy choosing. *Water and Ecology*. 25. 67-80. 10.23968/2305-3488.2020.25.4.67-80.